

Research Mapping the Operating Profit Margin (OPM) Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to determine research mapping around the Operating Profit Margin (OPM) ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking with mix-method approach, namely VOSviewer bibliometric studies and Library Researchs. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the OPM ratio; (2) mapping the results of VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the OPM ratio based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around the OPM ratio using a Library Research study. The research results show that: (1) based on mapping the distribution of journal publications, there are 23 journal publications regarding the OPM ratio; (2) based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, network visualization results around the OPM ratio are divided into 3 clusters and 75 topic items; (3) based on mapping Library Research studies, there are 15 topics surrounding the OPM ratio. Implications and contributions This research is to map research topics regarding the OPM ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Operating Profit Margin (OPM), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Library Research, Sharia and Conventional Banking

Introduction

Operating Profit Margin (OPM) is a financial ratio used to measure a company's efficiency in generating profits from its core operations. This ratio shows what percentage of operating income becomes profit before interest and tax expenses are deducted. In the banking industry, this ratio is very important because these companies rely on operating income as their main source of income. The development of the use of the OPM ratio in the banking industry is mainly influenced by several factors. First, the banking industry is currently experiencing pressure from increasingly fierce competition, especially from fast-growing financial technology (fintech) companies. Therefore, banks must improve their operational efficiency to remain competitive (Ujiandari, 2015). Second, the role of regulation also has an impact on the use of the OPM ratio in the banking industry. Strict banking regulations encourage banks to improve their operational efficiency and optimize the use of their capital. The OPM ratio is used as an indicator of success in achieving this goal (Nazira, 2016). Third, technological developments also influence the use of the OPM ratio in the banking industry. Technological developments have enabled banks to increase their operational efficiency and reduce costs. Banks that utilize technology to automate their business processes and increase their operational efficiency tend to have higher OPM (Muhamad et al., 2020). Fourth, the use of analytical data is also increasingly important in the banking industry. Today's banks are increasingly using data analytics to identify opportunities to improve their operational efficiency and optimize the use of their capital. The OPM ratio is used as a tool to monitor progress in achieving this goal. Overall, the OPM ratio is an important performance indicator for the banking industry (Daud, 2017). The use of this ratio will become increasingly important as the banking industry continues to develop and competition becomes

increasingly fierce. Banks that successfully increase their OPM tend to be more efficient and more profitable than their competitors. Therefore, banks must continue to improve their operational efficiency and monitor their OPM ratios regularly to achieve future success.

Research on OPM in banking has become an important topic and has attracted the attention of many researchers in the financial sector. Some of the latest research developments related to the OPM ratio in the banking industry include: first, several studies have been conducted to analyze the influence of internal and external factors on OPM in banking. Internal factors such as bank size, capital structure and risk management, while external factors such as interest rates and economic growth (Damayanti, 2016). Second, several studies use regression models to analyze the relationship between OPM and the factors that influence it. This regression model can help to identify the factors that most influence OPM in banking (Agustina, 2020). Third, several studies have been conducted to compare OPM between conventional banks and Islamic banks. This research aims to understand the differences in financial performance between the two types of banks and what factors influence them (Maesaroh, 2021). Fourth, several studies were also carried out using a case study approach at certain banks to analyze the factors that influence OPM at that bank. Overall, research on OPM in banking has become the main focus for researchers in the financial sector. This is because OPM is an important financial ratio and can provide important information regarding operational efficiency and company profitability (Mawardi, 2018). Through this research, it is hoped that it can help decision making for banking industry players and increase our understanding of the factors that influence bank financial performance.

The aim of this research is to map research around the OPM ratio in Banking using: (1) bibliometric methods VOSviewer to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications a scientific field by creating metadata network maps; and (2) Library Research studies to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding the OPM ratio. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research OPM. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics regarding the OPM ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Operating Profit Margin (OPM) or Operating Profit Margin is a financial ratio used to measure a company's efficiency and profitability in generating profits from their core operations. In the banking context, OPM refers to the ratio between operating profit or operating income and net income. In other words, banking OPM measures how efficient a bank is in generating profits from its core operations, such as lending activities, risk management and investment management. The higher the OPM, the more efficient the bank is in generating operating profits. OPM can be calculated by dividing operating profit by net income. For example, if a bank has an operating profit of 10 billion and a net income of 100 billion, then the bank's OPM is 10%. OPM is one of the key indicators of banking financial performance and is used by investors and financial analysts to evaluate a bank's profitability and operational efficiency. The higher the OPM of a bank, the more efficient and profitable the bank is (Moch, 2015).

Bibliometric studies are research methods used to analyze scientific publications and journals published in a particular scientific discipline or research field. This method uses quantitative and statistical data to measure and map research trends and patterns in a research field. Bibliometric studies involve collecting bibliographic data from sources such as journal databases, scientific publications,

and citation indexes, and using statistical analysis to evaluate and map publications and citations related to a particular topic or subfield. Some of the information that can be gleaned from bibliometric studies are research trends, the most frequently discussed topics, the most cited journals, the most productive institutions and researchers, and how quickly the research is disseminated within the scientific community. Bibliometric studies are widely used in academic and industrial research to measure research impact, evaluate academic performance, and assist decision making in managing research and development resources in an institution or organization (Dubyna et al., 2022).

VOSviewer is free software used for visualization and analysis of bibliometric data. This software is widely used in academic research to analyze scientific publication and citation patterns, as well as map the conceptual framework of a research field. VOSviewer can be used to visualize the relationship between keywords, authors, institutions, and research topics in the form of a network diagram which can help researchers to understand the relationship between these elements visually. These network diagrams can be customized in various ways, such as by changing the size of the nodes or the lines that represent the relationships between nodes. VOSviewer can also be used to analyze citation and co-citation patterns from scientific publications, and can show the occurrence of the most frequently discussed terms and topics in a research field. In this way, VOSviewer helps visually map the conceptual framework of a research field and provides deeper insight into emerging research topics. VOSviewer can be used by researchers and librarians to perform bibliometric analyzes and to develop more comprehensive Library Researchs in certain research areas (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Library Research study is a research method used to study and evaluate literature and scientific publications that have been published in a particular research field. This method involves the identification, assessment, and synthesis of relevant literature in a specified research area. Library Research studies are conducted to gather information and update understanding about a particular research topic. This method can help identify trends, themes and research patterns that are developing in a research field, as well as help researchers understand the debates and perspectives that exist in the literature. The steps in a Library Research study include identifying relevant literature sources, evaluating the quality and accuracy of the information contained in the literature, and synthesizing the information to develop a broader and more comprehensive understanding of the research topic. Library Research studies are an important research method in science, especially in preparing Library Researchs and literature research. Library Research studies can also be used as a basis for developing a broader theory or conceptual framework in a specified research field (El-Halaby et al., 2021).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is Operating Profit Margin (OPM). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on OPM in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and the Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category including the key words " Operating Profit Margin " and "OPM" within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals that have been published collected the data; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding OPM using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping bibliometric network visualization results and journal publication trends around OPM using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around OPM using Library Research studies (Budianto, 2023) (Gozali et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rofika et al., 2023) (Budianto, Dewi, et al., 2023) (Budianto, Saputra, et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto & Dewi, 2022) (Emiliani et al., 2023).

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications regarding Operating Profit Margin (OPM) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 23 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2013 to 2022. The results are as follows:

Table 1. OPM journal publication data by year

Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication
2013	1	2017	3	2020	4
2015	3	2018	3	2021	3
2016	2	2019	1	2022	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Vosviewer Bibliometric Study Mapping of Operating Profit Margin (OPM) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Article search results in Perish/Harzing software are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around OPM. Source:

Data processed, VOSViewer 1.6.18 software.

the VOSViewer software visualization regarding the research development map regarding OPM in Sharia and Conventional Banking, there are 3 clusters and 75 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, consists of 33 topic items, namely: Indonesian stock exchange, data, debt, earnings per share, Indonesian securities, EPS, GPM, gross profit margin, stock prices, hypothesis, independent variable, data analysis methods, multiple linear regression, multiple regression analysis, nom, opm, pbv, influence of price book value/return, population, profit margin, purposive sampling, ratio, return, roe, secondary data, share, significant effect, significant on stock prices, spss version, stock price.
- Cluster 2, consists of 22 topic items, namely: analysis method, assets, Indonesian stock exchange, company, earnings management, effects, hypothesis testing, IDX, income smoothing, Indonesian stock exchange, leverage, logistic regression, multiple linear regression, net profit margin, operating profit margin, influence, price earning ratio, profitability, purposive sampling method, roa, size.
- Cluster 3, consists of 20 topic items, namely: cash flow, dividend payout ratio/policy, effect cash flow, effect investment opportunity, equity, fcount value, table, influence investment opportunity, investment opportunity, metal company, operating activity, dividend policy, quantitative approach, regression analysis technique, research objective, significant influence, significant level.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Operating Profit Margin (OPM) Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 10 topics regarding the OPM ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, the influence of Earning Per Share (EPS) on OPM. OPM and EPS are two important financial performance indicators for banks. OPM measures the percentage of each dollar of sales generated as profit before interest and taxes are deducted, while EPS measures the profit per share received by shareholders. The effect of OPM on EPS in banking can vary depending on the specific situation of the bank. However, in general, high OPM can have a positive influence on EPS in banking. This is because if banks are able to maintain a high OPM, then they can generate more profit from each dollar of sales. In the long term, this can increase net profit and EPS. A high OPM can also show that the bank has a good business strategy and is efficient in managing operational costs. However, it should be noted that an OPM that is too high can also be a sign that the bank is not investing enough resources in long-term growth and development. This can cause slow or even declining profit growth in the long term, and a negative impact on EPS. Therefore, while high OPM can have a positive influence on EPS in banking, there needs to be a balance between operational efficiency and investment for long-term growth.

Second, the influence of efficient use of business capital on OPM. The efficiency of using business capital measures how well a company utilizes the capital it has to generate profits. In a banking context, OPM can provide an overview of how well a company manages its operations and generates profits. The higher the OPM of a bank, the more efficient the bank is in managing its operations. However, a high OPM can also be an indication that the bank is charging high fees to its customers. Meanwhile, the efficiency of using business capital can provide an idea of how well the company utilizes its capital to generate profits. The higher the efficiency of a bank's use of business capital, the more efficient the bank is in utilizing its capital to generate profits. In relation to banking, high OPM can contribute positively to the efficient use of business capital. This is because the more efficient a bank is in generating profits from its operations, the higher the profits generated by the bank from the capital it has. In this way, the efficiency of using business capital will increase. However, it should be noted that the relationship between OPM and the

efficiency of using business capital is not always linear and depends on various other factors such as operational costs, credit risk, and management policies. Therefore, the use of OPM as an indicator of the efficiency of business capital use in banking must be considered carefully and cannot be used as the only indicator.

Third, the influence of share prices on OPM. OPM can influence stock prices in banks because investors pay attention to the company's ability to generate consistent and growing profits from main business operations. An increase in OPM shows that the company has succeeded in managing its operational costs effectively and/or increasing its operational income. This shows ability company to generate greater profits from its main operations and can demonstrate the company's financial stability. As a result, investors may be more interested in buying shares in the company and increase the share price. On the other hand, a decrease in OPM can indicate problems in the company's business operations, such as an increase in operating costs or a decrease in revenue. This can cause investors to lose confidence in the company and sell their shares, which can lower the share price. However, it is important to remember that OPM is only one factor that influences stock prices and other factors such as net income, earnings growth, other financial ratios, and overall economic conditions also contribute to stock price assessments.

Fourth, the influence of dividend policy on OPM. In the banking industry, OPM can influence dividend policy. The higher the OPM, the greater the bank's ability to pay dividends to shareholders. Banks that have low OPM may have to consider withholding dividend payments to secure sufficient capital to strengthen their financial strength. However, keep in mind that dividend policy is also influenced by many other factors such as cash flow, business growth, future projections and applicable regulations. Therefore, OPM is not the only factor that influences dividend policy in banks. In addition, banks usually have their own policies and regulations regarding dividend payments which vary in each country. Thus, the influence of OPM on dividend policy in banking can vary depending on the specific situation and conditions of each company and country.

Fifth, the influence of earnings management on OPM. In the banking industry, OPM can influence earnings management practices. The higher the OPM, the less incentive there is for management to practice earnings management, because the profits from operational activities are already quite large. Conversely, if OPM is low, management will have an incentive to carry out earnings management practices to show better performance. However, it is important to remember that OPM is only one factor that influences earnings management practices, and there are other factors that can also influence it, such as pressure to meet financial performance targets, strict regulations, and other factors that are subjective in nature. Therefore, the influence of OPM on earnings management practices needs to be seen in the context of other factors that can also influence these practices.

Sixth, the influence of company value on OPM. OPM can influence company value in banking because: (1) It shows good operational performance: a high OPM shows that the company has the ability to generate quite large profits from its business operations. This indicates that the company has good operational performance, which can increase investor confidence and increase company value. (2) Shows good cost efficiency: High OPM can also show that the company has good cost control and high operational efficiency. This can improve the company's financial performance and strengthen its position in the market, which in turn can increase company value. (3) Increase the ability to obtain funding: A high OPM can increase a company's ability to obtain funding, such as loans from banks or investors. This can help companies develop their business and increase company value. However, it is also important to remember that OPM should not be the only factor considered in assessing a company's value to banks. There are other factors such as credit risk, liquidity, market growth, and macroeconomic factors that must also be considered.

Seventh, the effect of changes in profit on OPM. In the banking industry, OPM can significantly influence changes in profits. The higher the OPM, the greater the possibility that the company can generate greater profits. However, it is important to remember that OPM is not the only factor that influences changes in banking profits. There are several other factors that also have an influence, such as credit risk, funding costs and investment profits. Banking also has different business characteristics with other industries, such as interest rate regulation by central banks and strict regulations from regulatory authorities. Apart from that, OPM can also be influenced by external factors such as economic conditions, competition in the banking industry, and changes in government policy. In this case, it is necessary to carry out a more in-depth and comprehensive analysis to determine the influence of OPM on changes in banking profits specifically. However, in general, OPM can be an important indicator in measuring banking operational efficiency and can influence changes in profits for the company.

Eighth, the effect of income smoothing on OPM. In banking, a high OPM can reduce the need for income smoothing due to naturally more stable profits. In this case, banks with high OPM tend to have stable revenue and cost curves, resulting in more consistent profits over time. In contrast, banks with low OPM tend to experience greater fluctuations in income and costs, and are therefore more likely to carry out income smoothing to maintain profit stability. However, it is important to note that the effect of OPM on income smoothing is not always linear or unidirectional. There are many other factors that influence income practices smoothing banking, such as regulations, credit risk and market conditions. Therefore, it is important to analyze these factors holistically when considering the influence of OPM on income smoothing practices in banking.

Ninth, procedures for using OPM. OPM differs from NPM as a measure of a company's ability to generate profits. The difference is that OPM is based only on the company's operations ignoring the funding costs of interest payments and taxes. For example, OPM can be used in situations where the party wishing to purchase a company through a buyout is in debt. When buyers analyze a target company, they will look for potential improvements they can bring to its operations. OPM provides insight into how well a target company is performing compared to its peers, especially how efficiently the company is managing its expenses to maximize profits. Eliminating interest and taxes helps because an indebted purchase would inject the company with new debt that would make historical interest costs irrelevant. A company's OPM indicates how well the company is managed because operational costs such as salaries, rent and equipment rental are variable costs, not fixed costs. A company may have little control over direct production costs such as the cost of raw materials needed to produce the company's products. However, company management has a lot of discretion in matters such as how much they choose to spend on office rent, equipment, and staff. Therefore, a company's operating profit margin is usually considered a superior indicator of the strength of a company's management team, compared to gross profit margin or net profit.

Tenth, limitations on the use of the OPM ratio. As in any part of financial analysis, any number of interest requires additional research to understand the reasons behind the number. Discrepancies in OPM between peer companies can be caused by various factors. For example, a company pursuing an outsourcing strategy may report different profit margins than a company producing in-house. In comparing companies, depreciation methods can result in changes in operating profit margins. Companies using the double declining balance depreciation method may report lower profit margins that increase over time even if there is no change in efficiency. Companies using the straight-line depreciation method will see constant margins unless other factors change as well. The general rule is to keep factors such as geography, company size, industry, and business model constant when using operating profit margin as a comparative analysis between peer companies. It is also

useful to consider other profitability metrics in addition, such as Profit Margin Gross or OPM, as well as other financial metrics such as leverage, efficiency, and market value ratios.

Eleventh, internal factors that influence OPM, include: (1) Production volume: Higher or lower output can reduce or increase profit margins, because the company's fixed costs are distributed to higher or lower sales resulting from increased or decreased production. (2) Price: An increase or decrease in the price of a service or product can change operating margins. (3) Cost of goods sold: Changes in direct production costs can affect a company's operating margin. For example, increasing wages for factory workers can reduce margins, while switching to lower-cost suppliers can increase them. (4) Selling, general, and administrative costs: These costs, also known as overhead, do not change much when production increases or decreases. Companies often cut these costs when they target long-term operating margin improvements. For example, if a company wants to reduce rental costs, they may have to move to a smaller, less expensive office space. (5) Depreciation and amortization charges: These charges do not involve cash and are based on the estimated loss in productive value of the company's assets. This is an accounting device that spreads the cost of purchasing an asset over a period of time, rather than all at once. For example, if a company purchases workstations and laptops for the office and sales staff and depreciates their value over five years, those costs will reduce operating profits for that time period.

Twelfth, external factors that influence OPM include: (1) Economic conditions: A growing economy benefits most companies, and vice versa when the economy shrinks. A growing economy means consumers have more income to spend, giving businesses the opportunity to sell more, increase production, and spread their fixed costs over more output. (2) Demand: Products that are in demand usually benefit a company's sales, profits, and operating profit margins, because the company can sell more, charge higher prices, or both. Weak demand and declining sales are putting a strain on margins. (3) Competition: Little or no competition may free a company to increase prices or production, increasing operating margins. Competitive markets and insufficient product supply hinder a company's ability to increase prices or production.

Thirteenth, how to increase OPM. To increase operational profit margins, there are two simple ways that can be done, namely by increasing sales and reducing costs. A business can increase sales by raising prices or increasing production output. Conversely, businesses can also reduce production costs (COGS) or selling, general, and administrative costs (SG&A). Businesses have more direct control over SG&A costs, which can be reduced in several ways. For example, a business can rent a smaller office, make layoffs, or cut advertising costs. Meanwhile, reducing COGS costs may be more difficult because workers may refuse to accept reductions in wages and benefits, and suppliers of goods may reject requests for price reductions. To widen their operational profit margins, businesses often consider expanding the scale of their operations to gain greater economies of scale, thereby obtaining more output at lower unit costs. Businesses can expand their operations internally by producing more, adding new products, or entering new markets. Alternatively, a business can also expand its operations externally by acquiring other businesses.

Fourteenth, there are several shortcomings in using the OPM ratio in measuring financial performance ratios. This is because OPM does not provide complete information. Some other things to consider include: (1) Non-operating results: For example, a company's income from investments increases net income, but does not affect operating income. This could indicate that the company is relying on something else to improve profitability. (2) Restructuring costs: One-time operating costs to restructure in an effort to restore or improve profitability will hurt margins in the short term. (3) Interest and taxes: Interest on debt and taxes are not factored into operating profit, so companies must understand how much operating

profit is available to pay these costs. Businesses with high operating margins are better able to handle interest and tax expenses. (4) Cash flow: This is usually different from profit, which usually includes some costs excluded from cash flow. Cash flow is usually the strongest predictor of a company's value, especially when analyzed using a technique known as discounted cash flow, which shows how much a dollar in the future is worth today. (5) Growth rate: An established company may have high operating margins but a lower growth rate, while a newer, fast-growing company with high costs may report operating losses in its early years.

Fifteenth, ideal OPM. There are 3 questions regarding this topic, namely: (1) What is a good OPM? Good OPM is relative depending on the industry and whether a company has high non-operating costs, such as taxes and interest on debt, or restructuring costs. For example, a good OPM might be 25% if other companies in the industry are only generating 15% margins. Meanwhile, a continuously widening OPM shows that the company is succeeding in important aspects of its operations. (2) Is a high OPM good or bad? High OPM is clearly better than low. Companies that borrow to buy assets, for example, want wider margins so they can pay debt interest and taxes while still having a significant amount to count as net income. However, what is more important than a specific percentage is looking back at OPM over time. Varying or irregular OPM can be a sign of problems a company is having in maintaining output and prices, or in controlling costs. (3) What are the consequences of having a low OPM? A business with low OPM may have to make difficult decisions. They can initiate efforts to increase sales, but that may mean spending more on sales staff or providing price discounts to attract customers. They can also try to negotiate lower prices from suppliers or change suppliers. Businesses with low profit margins may also have difficulty getting loans or attracting investors.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the number of research publications regarding the Operating Profit Margin (OPM) ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2013 to 2022 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 23 journal articles publication. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the NOM ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 3 clusters and 75 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 33 topics, cluster 2 consists of 22 topics, and cluster 3 consists of 20 topics. Third, based on mapping of Library Research studies, there are 15 OPM ratios in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Earning Per Share (EPS), efficiency of use of business capital, share prices, dividend policy, earnings management, company value, changes in profits, income smoothing/ income smoothing, procedures for using OPM, limitations on using the OPM ratio, internal and external factors that influence OPM, how to increase OPM, several disadvantages of using the OPM ratio in measuring financial performance ratios, and the ideal OPM.

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